

Online workshop of the author team, 29.09.2023

Results from the workshop (miro board):

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How can SSH approaches address these gaps?

How do we define SSH?

Solutions, concrete proposals, examples

What should our single policy recommendation / title be?

1. To manage the risks and opportunities of the energy system transformation, policy should broaden its evidence base to include inter- and transdisciplinary research as well as the learnings from implementation projects.
2. Applying a justice lens to energy system models for fair and timely climate neutral pathways'

